

MATHEMATICAL-STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF PROVIDING IMPROVED-QUALITY REMOTE MEDICAL CARE TO MILITARY PERSONNEL

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Annotation: In this article: to bring the medical service provided to military personnel to the level of international requirements, to call for reliable service in any, difficult, field and extreme conditions without hesitation with a high probability. The methods currently being introduced in the troops of the Ministry of Defense and proposed by us play an incomparable role in achieving time efficiency in organizing qualified medical care, the role of the information and communication system. The correlation between the current and proposed methods is analyzed based on the linear regression equation.

Key words: A_1 – the value of the magnitude in the initial state; A_2 – the value of the magnitude in the subsequent state. The need for remote communication between patients and injured military personnel and qualified doctors in epidemiological and field conditions, mathematical statistical calculations. Regression coefficient r_{xy} . The correlation relationship turns into a functional relationship.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada: harbiy xizmatchilarga ko‘rsatiladigan tibbiy xizmatni xalqaro talablar darajasiga chiqarish, har qanday, qiyin, dala va ekstrimal sharoitlarda hech ikkilanmasdan katta ehtimollik bilan ishonchli xizmat qilishga chorlash. Hozirgi kunda Mudofaa vazirgi qo‘shinlarida joriy qilinayotgan va biz tomonimizdan taklif etilgan usullarning malakali shifokor yordamini tashkil qilishda vaqt samadorililigiga erishishda axborot-kommunikatsiya tizimining o‘rni beqiyos ekanligi. Joriy va taklif etilgan usullar orasida korrelyatsiyali bog‘lanishning chiziqli regressiya tenglamasi asosida tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: A_1 – dastlabki holatdagi kattalikning qiymati; A_2 – keyingi holatdagi kattalikning qiymati. Epidemiologik holatlar va dala sharoitida bemorlar hamda jarohat olgan harbiy xizmatchilar bilan malakali shifokorlar orasida masofali muloqotni talab etishi zarurati, matematik statistika hisoblar. Regressiya koeffitsienti r_{xy} Korrelatsion bog‘lanish funksional bog‘lanishga o‘tadi.

Аннотация: В данной статье: довести медицинское обслуживание военнослужащих до уровня международных требований, без колебаний и с высокой вероятностью призвать к надежной службе в любых, сложных, полевых и экстремальных условиях. Предлагаемые нами методы, внедряемые в настоящее время в войсках Министерства обороны, играют непревзойденную роль в достижении оперативности организации квалифицированной медицинской помощи, роль информационно-коммуникационной системы. На основе уравнения линейной регрессии проанализирована корреляция между действующими и предлагаемыми методами.

Ключевые слова: A_1 – величина в начальном состоянии; A_2 – величина в последующем состоянии. Эпидемиологические ситуации и условия полевых действий требуют организации дистанционного взаимодействия между пациентами и ранеными военнослужащими с

квалифицированными врачами, а также проведения расчетов математической статистики. Коэффициент регрессии r_{xy} . Корреляционная связь переходит в функциональную зависимость.

Time is a crucial quantity for human life, characterized by its exceptional value and limited nature. Throughout life, a person often requires assistance from others. In many cases, military personnel also need the support of others during service. In such situations, the help of a specialist becomes essential—these specialists are medical workers. Since medical personnel have designated workplaces at medical points, it becomes necessary to transport sick or injured military personnel to medical facilities. Naturally, this requires the use of transport vehicles [1].

For qualified physicians, both the time required to deliver the patient (t_e) and the waiting time for admission (t_k) play an important role in determining the outcome of a human life. Therefore, due to the high probability of adverse events and the low efficiency of medical care, time allocation always becomes critical. The faster a patient receives treatment, the greater the likelihood of saving their life. In the current system, the total time for providing medical care consists of two parts:

$$t_{\text{total}} = t_e + t_k \quad (1)$$

Thus, the time required in the current system is expressed by Formula (1), where: t_e – time required to deliver the patient to a qualified doctor via transport (minutes), t_k – waiting time for a qualified physician’s admission (minutes).

We propose using telemedicine devices based on modern information technologies, which enable on-site diagnosis of patients. When using such telemedicine systems, the time t_e becomes zero, and only t_k remains relevant. This reduces the overall time required for medical care, thereby ensuring higher-quality medical assistance and increasing efficiency. Since efficiency is considered the main parameter in medicine, it can be determined using the classical formula [3]:

$$C = \frac{|A_2 - A_1|}{A_2} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where:

C – coefficient representing the efficiency of medical service;

A₁ – initial value of the parameter;

A₂ – improved value of the parameter.

If we substitute time parameters into Formula (2), we can calculate the efficiency of medical service under extreme or harsh field conditions:

$$C = \frac{|t_e - t_k|}{t_e} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

Given:

$t_k = 4$ hours

$t_e = 9$ hours

Using Formula (3), we obtain the following:

$$C_j = \frac{|9 - 4|}{9} \times 100\% = \frac{5 \times 100}{9} = 55.5\%$$

Thus, under the classical method, the time efficiency of providing qualified medical assistance is 55.5%. Here, C_j represents the time-efficiency indicator for medical support currently implemented in the armed forces [2].

If the evaluation scale takes 100% as the ideal benchmark, an efficiency score between 55% and 70% corresponds to the “satisfactory” category. For modern science and medical advancements, this indicator may not fully meet contemporary requirements. Especially during epidemiological situations and field conditions, there is a need for remote communication between patients or injured military personnel and qualified physicians. Therefore, the relevance of the proposed method lies in the ability to utilize information and telecommunication technologies at a high level, which—economically, socially, and medically—provides a strong likelihood of significantly increasing overall efficiency [5,6]. In calculating the efficiency of the method, we propose, the value of t_j remains unchanged, while t_T —according to the results of our scientific research and practical experiments—has an optimal value of up to 45 minutes. Considering that 45 minutes corresponds to 0.75 hours, its efficiency can be calculated as follows:

$$C_2 = \frac{|9 - 0.75|}{9} \times 100\% = \frac{8.25 \times 100}{9} = 91.6\%$$

Thus, after applying the proposed method, the time-efficiency of qualified medical assistance equals 91.6%. To determine the efficiency gain of our proposed approach, we use the following difference-of-efficiencies formula:

$$\Delta C = C_2 - C_1 = 91.6 - 55.5 = 36\%$$

Here:

C_2 - time-efficiency of the proposed method,

C_1 - time-efficiency of the classical method.

This clearly shows that the efficiency of our proposed approach is 36% higher compared to the current system.

It is evident that both methods—the currently implemented system and the approach we propose—ultimately aim to improve the medical service system. Therefore, constructing correlation relationships and regression equations for both the current and proposed approaches is considered appropriate. For this purpose, a first table was created to simplify the mathematical-statistical calculations.

Table 1.

Mathematical–statistical analysis of time distribution

N _o	X_i	Y_i	X_i^2	Y_i^2	$X_i Y_i$	$Y_i - \bar{Y}_x = \delta$
	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	9	12	81	144	108	12-11,34=0,66
2	15	16	225	256	240	16-17,76=-1,76
3	22	27	484	729	594	27-25,25=1,75
4	28	31	784	961	868	31-31,67=-0,67
n= 4	$\sum X_i$ = 74	$\sum Y_i$ = 86	$\sum X_i^2$ = 1574	$\sum Y_i^2$ = 2090	$\sum X_i Y_i$ = 1810	

In addition, using Student’s statistical survey method, a mathematical–statistical analysis is conducted based on the data presented in Table 1 regarding the time spent by respondents at a military medical institution to reach a qualified physician and the waiting time for admission. Using the method of least squares and the results of Table 1, we construct the linear regression equation

$$y=ax+by = ax + by= ax+b$$

and to determine the parameters aaa and bbb, we form the following system of algebraic equations:

$$\begin{cases} b \sum_{i=1}^n X_i + a \sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i \\ b n + a \sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

There exist several methods for solving this system, including the Gauss–Jordan method, Cramer’s rule, substitution, algebraic elimination, and others.

$$74b + 1574a = 1810, \quad 4b + 74a = 86 \Rightarrow b = \frac{86 - 74a}{4} \quad (2)$$

Substituting

$$b = \frac{86 - 74a}{4}$$

to the first equation, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} 74 \left(\frac{86 - 74a}{4} \right) + 1574a &= 1810 \\ \Rightarrow \\ 6364 - 5476a + 6296a &= 7240; \end{aligned}$$

By solving the last equation for the parameter **a** and substituting it into formula (2), we obtain the linear

$$\bar{Y}_x = Y = ax + b$$

function:

$$820a = 876a = 1.068 \approx 1.07$$

Thus,

$$b = 86 - 79.184 = 1.705 \approx 1.71$$

Therefore, the required regression equation is obtained as:

$$Y = 1.07x + 1.71$$

For these two military institutions (the Special Emergency Recovery Directorate and military unit 71186), a scientific correlation analysis of the time spent on receiving medical services was performed, demonstrating that the difference between $Y_i Y_i$ and $\bar{Y}_x \bar{Y}_x$ is sufficiently small. This theoretical conclusion is supported by practical evidence; see column 6 of Table 1.

Figure 1 illustrates the graph of the linear regression equation representing the correlation between the time spent on receiving qualified medical care, based on the survey data from the Special Emergency Recovery Directorate and military unit 71186.

To determine the regression coefficients in scientific research, the following mathematical statistical formulas are used [3].

Figure 1. Linear regression graph representing the correlation between the time spent for receiving qualified medical care, based on survey data from the Special Emergency Recovery Directorate and military unit 71186.

$M(x) \approx \bar{X}$ the mathematical expectation of the random variable (Special Emergency Recovery Directorate);

$M(y) \approx \bar{Y}$ the mathematical expectation of the discrete random variable of military unit 71186, which is approximately equal to the arithmetic mean

$D(x); D(y)$ - the standard deviations and variances of the observations for the corresponding military units

C_{xy} -the covariance parameter;

r_{xy} - the correlation coefficient.

$$M(x) = \bar{X} = \frac{\sum X_i}{n} = \frac{74}{4} = 18,5$$

$$M(y) = \bar{Y} = \frac{\sum Y_i}{n} = \frac{86}{4} = 21.5$$

Variance and standard deviation:

$$Dx = \sigma_x^2 = \frac{\sum X_i^2}{n} - \bar{X}^2 = \frac{1574}{4} - 18.5^2 = 393.5 - 342.25 = 51.25$$

$$\sigma_x = \sqrt{51.25} = 7.16$$

$$Dy = \sigma_y^2 = \frac{\sum Y_i^2}{n} - \bar{Y}^2 = \frac{2090}{4} - 21.5^2 = 522.5 - 462.25 = 60.25;$$

$$\sigma_y = \sqrt{60.25} = 7.76$$

Covariance

$$C_{xy} = \frac{\sum X_i Y_i}{n} - \bar{X} * \bar{Y} = \frac{1810}{4} - 18.5 * 21.5 = 452.5 - 397.75 = 54.75;$$

Correlation coefficient:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{C_{xy}}{\tau_x * \tau_y} = \frac{54.75}{7.16 * 7.76} = 0.985;$$

The closer the regression coefficient r_{xy} is to 1, the stronger the correlation between the variables. If $r_{xy} = 1$, the correlation becomes a functional relationship. The value must satisfy the condition $|r_{xy}| \leq 1$, i. e. $-1 \leq r_{xy} \leq 1$.

CONCLUSION OF THE RESEARCH

The study demonstrates the need to raise the level of medical services to international standards. This ensures that military personnel can perform reliably and confidently in any difficult, field, or extreme conditions.

The article also shows that the efficiency of the current and proposed methods was evaluated using classical statistical approaches. Most importantly, it is proven that information and communication systems play an essential role in increasing the effectiveness of medical services.

A linear regression equation describing the correlation between the variables was developed for comparing the existing and proposed methods.

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